

Type-Based Genetic Algorithms

Roman Sizov · Dan A. Simovici

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Abstract This paper introduces a novel type-based genetic algorithm and its applications to the N -queen problem, travelling salesman problem, and finding the global minima of several well-known functions, such as the Rosenbrock function, the Rastrigin function, the Schwefel function, the Griewangk function and the Ackley function. The algorithm offers a new approach to internal structure of individuals in population of genetic algorithms.

Keywords genetic algorithm · type-based · gender-based · N -queen problem · Travelling Salesman Problem · Rosenbrock function · Rastrigin function · Schwefel function · Griewangk function · Ackley function

1 Introduction

Genetic algorithms have been successfully applied to find approximate solutions to NP -complete problems, e.g. travelling salesman problem (TSP) [8, 6] and multiprocessor scheduling [10].¹ Also, genetic algorithms have been applied to a multitude of multiobjective optimization problems: groundwater quality management [4], design of fuzzy autopilot controllers for engineering problems [3], etc. A comparative study of multi objective genetic algorithms and simulated annealing applied to analogue filter tuning was undertaken in [19]. In [11] an improved genetic algorithm to solve 0/1 multidimensional knapsack problem is introduced by proposing

Roman Sizov
Department of Computer Science,
University of Massachusetts, Boston, MA 02125, USA
E-mail: rsizov@cs.umb.edu

Dan A. Simovici
Department of Computer Science,
University of Massachusetts, Boston, MA 02125, USA
E-mail: Dan.Simovici@umb.edu

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new sexual selection and crossover operators that cooperate to explore the search space. A method of optimizing Quantitative Learner’s Motivation Model with the use of different types of genetic algorithms is presented in [12].

Classic genetic algorithms [5] have three main genetic operators: selection, mutation and crossover. Individuals (or chromosomes) for reproduction are determined by a selection operator based on their fitness function values. The offspring is produced by crossover of chromosomes of the parents. Also, mutation is applied with some low probability to change gene values in a chromosome. The mutation operator boosts the diversity in the population and thus increases the chances to avoid a local optima.

We introduce a novel type-based genetic algorithm where individuals are classified based on their internal chromosomal structure which determines their type. Our algorithm partitions the population of individuals into a set of types based on this structure, and allows mating only between individuals that belong to different types. We focus of two-type populations that contain one or two full chromosomes. Various genetic algorithms that split the population into types based on a gender were introduced in the past [16,20,2]. However, their approach only tags an individual as a male or a female and to not involve the chromosomal composition of individuals.

We demonstrate that our type-based genetic algorithm outperforms the classic genetic algorithms for several important problems: the N -Queen problem and finding the global minima of several much-explored functions. Namely, our algorithm produces solutions closer to the global optimum in fewer generations.

The paper is organized into sections as follows. Section 2 introduces the design of our type-based populations. Genetic operators for these populations are discussed in Section 3. Section 4 presents the details of the proposed genetic algorithm. The implementation of the algorithm, the performance analysis and some experimental results are discussed in Section 5. The article concludes with Section 6 which presents ideas for further work.

2 Structure of the Population

The population that evolves consists of individuals and is partitioned in a number of *types*.

Definition 21 Individuals have the following properties:

- each individual consists of one or more chromosomes, where each chromosome represents a solution to the problem solved by the genetic algorithm;
- each individual has a type, and there are at least two types;
- individuals can mate only with individuals of a different type.

□

We focus on populations that consist of two types of individuals designated as individuals of type \mathcal{A} and type \mathcal{B} , respectively defined as follows:

Definition 22 A type \mathcal{A} individual has two chromosomes of the same size.

A type \mathcal{B} individual is an individual with two chromosomes, the first one of which is of the same size as chromosomes in an individual of type \mathcal{A} and the second one is a *null chromosome*, i.e. a chromosome with the size 0.

The null chromosome is denoted by C_0 .

□

Figure 1 depicts type \mathcal{A} and type \mathcal{B} individuals, where one and two show the respective chromosomes of these individuals. Mating takes place between individuals of type \mathcal{A} and type \mathcal{B} and it proceeds as follows. A type \mathcal{A} parent provides one of its chromosome to its child in a random fashion. The child obtains the second chromosome from a type \mathcal{B} parent also in a random fashion. Note that the second chromosome may be a null chromosome.

The second chromosome of the child defines its type (i.e. type \mathcal{A} or type \mathcal{B}). We allow for the same parents to have several children. At this stage only four different children (two of type \mathcal{A} and two of type \mathcal{B}) could be born since each of the parent has two chromosomes. Nevertheless, since we allow for a crossover and a mutation with some small probability to occur, the offspring could be much more diverse.

The population size is fixed using a certain type of selection. However, the population size increases temporarily during the mating stage. Once the mating stage is complete, the population size is reduced to the original size by keeping only the most successful individuals. Also, note that since only different types of individuals can mate, we have to keep at least one individual of each type even if these individuals are not the most successful ones in the population. However, they still have to be the most successful in their type. Moreover, the initial population is created in a random fashion but at least one individual of each type must be present.

Fig. 1: Depiction of type \mathcal{A} and type \mathcal{B} Individuals

There are two kinds of chromosomes that we use in our algorithm. The first kind is a full chromosome with a fixed positive size L , where L is the number of genes in the chromosome. The second kind is a null chromosome C_0 with the size 0. This kind of chromosome is used to simplify the mating process and to automate the determination of the type of an individual.

Each full chromosome comprises L genes. Genes can have various types, e.g. an integer, a real number, an integer from a to b , a matrix or any other structure. In our algorithm the types of genes are fixed, i.e. a mutation process cannot change the type of a gene; only the value of a gene can be changed by mutation. Note

that chromosomes of the first kind can be heterogeneous (i.e. genes have different types) or homogeneous (i.e. all genes are of the same type).

The algorithm assumes that larger values of a fitness function mean a better solution. Fitness functions are normally applied to chromosomes and this is the case in our algorithm. However, we also allow for fitness functions to be applied to individuals.

Definition 23 Let \mathcal{C} be a chromosome space and let $f : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a fitness function, where $f(C_0) = -\infty$. Let $\mathcal{I} = \mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{C}$ be the space of individuals. Define a fitness function $F : \mathcal{I} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of an individual I as

$$F(I) = \max(f(C_1), f(C_2)),$$

where $I = (C_1, C_2)$. □

Note that a fitness function returns $-\infty$ for a null chromosome of a type \mathcal{B} individual. Thus, for a type \mathcal{B} individual I the fitness function is $F(I) = \max(f(C_1), f(C_0)) = \max(f(C_1), -\infty) = f(C_1)$.

3 Genetic Operators

The set of genetic operators that act on our populations consists of selections, mating, mutation and crossover.

3.1 Selection Operators

There are two selection operators in the algorithm since there are two different points when selection is necessary. The first selection is done to choose individuals from the population for mating. We choose the top α percent of the population with the provision that both best individuals from the type \mathcal{A} and the type \mathcal{B} must be present to guarantee that the mating process occurs.

The second selection happens after the mating process is complete. The best m individuals are chosen from the temporarily increased population, which includes both parents and their offspring in order to produce a population of the same size as the original population. Again, both best individuals from the type \mathcal{A} and the type \mathcal{B} must be present.

3.2 Mating Operator

Mating takes place only between individuals of type \mathcal{A} and type \mathcal{B} . The first chromosome is obtained by a child from an individual of type \mathcal{A} and the second chromosome is obtained from an individual of type \mathcal{B} .

The second chromosome defines the type of a child. If the child gets the first chromosome from the type \mathcal{B} parent, then the child is of type \mathcal{A} . On the other hand, if the child gets the second chromosome from the type \mathcal{B} parent, then the child is of type \mathcal{B} . Note that there is an exchange of genetic information on the individual level, i.e. exchange of actual chromosomes from two different individuals. This is very different from the classical crossover and mutation. This type of genetic information exchange cannot occur in a classic genetic algorithm.

3.3 Crossover Operator

Crossover may occur during the mating process. A crossover might occur with some probability in a type \mathcal{A} individual just before the mating with an individual of type \mathcal{B} since the type \mathcal{A} individual has two full chromosomes. The crossover does not change the type \mathcal{A} individual but only affects the child. Existing individuals do not change either through a crossover or a mutation. Note that there is another possibility for a crossover to occur. Namely, if a child of type \mathcal{A} is created, then there could be a crossover between chromosomes obtained from the parents. However, we have decided not to implement this crossover since it only affects type \mathcal{A} individuals. The crossover that we have implemented affects both types of newly born individuals. Note that a crossover operator acts at the chromosome level, i.e. it does not affect genes; they are exchanged between chromosomes without changing internal values of genes.

3.4 Mutation Operator

A mutation operator acts at both chromosome and gene levels. Mutation can occur in both chromosomes and their genes of both types of individuals. Note that for a type \mathcal{A} individuals both chromosomes and their genes might mutate. Mutation occurs with some small probability. On the chromosome level the genes subjected to mutation are randomly chosen but the actual mutation happens at the gene level.

Once a gene is chosen to be mutated, then it is up to the gene to decide how to mutate and to what extent. Mutation occurs with some small probability in both parents just before the mating process. However, it does not affect the parents (i.e. copies of the parents mutate; these copies are discarded later) but does affect the offspring.

4 Evolutionary Algorithm Design

The pseudocode of our algorithm is shown in Algorithm 1. Algorithm 1 uses the procedure in Algorithm 2.

The selection operator gets a population and a fitness function and returns a subpopulation based on internal criteria of the operator, e.g. best 25% individuals in the population.

There are two selection operators in the algorithm and they may have different internal criteria. Both of the operators must return the population with at least one type \mathcal{A} individual and one type \mathcal{B} individual.

The mating operator gets one type \mathcal{A} individual, one type \mathcal{B} from the population and a crossover operator, and returns a non-empty set of children produced by these individuals. This operator may or may not give some preference to either type of individuals produced. For example, we may impose a 60% probability for a child to be a type \mathcal{B} individual.

Also, it is up to the mating operator to decide on the probability of crossover occurrence. The crossover operator gets a pair of full chromosomes and changes the

obtained pair. The operator defines both a type of crossover and its probability. Note this operator does not return anything.

The mutation operator gets an individual and applies mutations to this individual with some probability that is internally defined. When the mutation operator affects some gene, then it is up to this gene to decide how to mutate. Note that this operator does not return anything.

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Input : Population size  $p \geq 2$ , Number of Generations  $n > 0$ ,
          Chromosome Template  $C$ , Selection Operator  $S_1$ , Selection
          Operator  $S_2$ , Mating Operator  $M$ , Crossover Operator  $R$ ,
          Mutation Operator  $U$ , Fitness Function  $F$ 
Output: Individual with highest fitness function value
begin
   $P \leftarrow \text{createInitialPopulation}(p, C);$           /* Creates initial random
  population */
  for  $i = 1$  to  $n$  do
     $P \leftarrow S_1(P, F);$           /* First selection operator is applied */
    while  $\text{size}(P) \leq 2p$  do
      Randomly choose a type  $\mathcal{A}$  individual from the population and
      set it to  $I_1$ ;
       $I_1 \leftarrow \text{copy of } I_1$ ;
      Randomly choose a type  $\mathcal{B}$  individual from the population and
      set it to  $I_2$ ;
       $I_2 \leftarrow \text{copy of } I_2$ ;
       $\text{Offspring} \leftarrow M(I_1, I_2, R);$           /* Mating operator is applied
      with crossover operator applied internally */
      Apply the mutation operator  $U$  to each child in  $\text{Offspring}$ ;
      Add  $\text{Offspring}$  to  $P$ ;
    end
     $P \leftarrow S_2(P, F);$           /* Second selection operator is applied and
    returns a subpopulation with the size equal to  $p$  */
  end
  return An individual from the population  $P$  with the highest value of the
  fitness function
end

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Algorithm 1: Type-Based Genetic Algorithm

5 Implementation and Experimental Results

We implemented our algorithm in Java-8 and used it for three distinct problems: the N -Queen problem, the Travelling Salesman Problem, and finding the global minima of several functions that are prominent in the optimization algorithms in genetic algorithms literature, namely the Rosenbrock, Rastrigin, Schwefel, Griewangk, and Ackley functions. Each of these problems has its own fitness function and structure of full chromosomes. However, the genetic operators, population structure and all constants used in the algorithm are the same.

5.1 N -Queen Problem

The N -Queen problem is the problem of placing N chess queens on an $N \times N$ chessboard so that no two queens attack each other. We used $N = 25$ and also applied the classic genetic algorithm to this problem [5].

The structure of a chromosome contains 25 genes, where a value of each gene is just an integer from 1 to 25. Each gene value represents a row on the 25×25 chessboard, where the column is the position of the gene in the chromosome, i.e. a number from 1 to 25. Thus, each column has only one queen and hence there are no other queen attacks on the column. The fitness function of a chromosome for this problem is the number of queen attacks on the chessboard taken with the negative sign. So, the maximum of the fitness function is 0, which represents a perfect solution to the problem. Note that this problem has many equally good solutions and the algorithm returns only one of them.

Figure 2 shows the results of applying our genetic algorithm and the classic genetic algorithm to the N -Queen problem.

Our algorithm is shown to produce much more stable results without losing their quality. In fact, the obtained solutions are better with the use of our genetic algorithm in contrast with the classic genetic algorithm. The stability of our algorithm is likely due to the fact that type \mathcal{A} individuals keep two solutions to the problem and, as a result, they have a higher chance to survive and archive the already found solutions, whereas in the classic algorithm all individuals have only one solution and, as a result, they are more likely to lose it due to crossovers and mutations. In our algorithm we have individuals that can save older solutions (namely, type \mathcal{A} individuals) and also individuals that are open to explore solution space in order to find possibly better new solutions to the problem (namely type \mathcal{B} individuals).

5.2 Finding Global Minima of Numerical Function

The *Rosenbrock function* is a non-convex function, introduced in 1960 in [15]. This function has only one global minimum and many local minima. Thus, it is a good candidate to test our algorithm and is defined as

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} [100(x_{i+1} - x_i^2)^2 + (1 - x_i)^2],$$

where $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

It is easy to see that the global minimum is at $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = (1, 1, \dots, 1)$ and equals 0. We used $n = 10$ for this problem and we only looked at the range of $[-10, 10]$ for each of the variables.

For this function (and for each of the functions examined) a full chromosome contains $n = 10$ genes, where each gene represents the i^{th} variable where $1 \leq i \leq 10$; also i is the position of the gene in the chromosome. Each gene is represented by an integer in $[-d, d]$, and in order to obtain the value of a variable the integer is divided by 100. For the Rosenbrock function, $d = 1000$.

The fitness function of a chromosome for each of these problems is the function to be minimized taken with negative sign; thus, the optimization problem amounts to maximizing the fitness function.

Fig. 2: Average (over 5 runs) Fitness Function Value vs. Number of Generation for N-Queen Problem, where N=25

The *Rastrigin function* is a non-convex function, first proposed by Rastrigin in 1974 [14] as a 2-dimensional function and generalized in [13]. Finding the minimum of this function is a difficult problem due to its large search space and its large number of local minima. The function is defined as

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = 10n + \sum_{i=1}^n [x_i^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi x_i)]$$

for $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Its global minimum equals 0 and is obtained for $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = (0, 0, \dots, 0)$.

Each variable ranges in $[-5.12, 5.12]$ and $d = 512$.

The *Schwefel function* [17] is challenging in that its global minimum is geometrically distant from the next best local minimum. Therefore, the algorithms are potentially prone to convergence in the wrong direction. The function defined by

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n [-x_i \sin(\sqrt{|x_i|})],$$

where $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Its global minimum is at

$$(420.9687, 420.9687, \dots, 420.9687)$$

and equals $-418.9829n$. In this case, $d = 50000$, so the range is $[-500, 500]$ for each of the variables. The maximum of the fitness function is 4189.829 , which represents the perfect solution to the problem.

The *Griewangk function* [9] has many widespread local minima regularly distributed. The function defined by

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \frac{1}{4000} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \prod_{i=1}^n \cos\left(\frac{x_i}{\sqrt{i}}\right) + 1,$$

where $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Its global minimum is at $(0, 0, \dots, 0)$ and equals 0. Also, $d = 60000$, so the range is $[-600, 600]$ for each of the variables.

Finally, the *Ackley function* is a non-convex function used as a performance test problem for optimization algorithms. It was proposed in [1]. This function is defined by

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = -a \exp\left(-b \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \cos(cx_i)\right) + a + \exp(1),$$

where $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$. We set $a = 20, b = 0.2, c = 2\pi$. Its global minimum is at $(0, 0, \dots, 0)$ and equals 0. We only looked at the range of $[-32.77, 32.77]$ for each of the variables, that is, $d = 3277$.

Figures 3,4,5,6,7 show the results of applying genetic algorithms to the problem of finding global minima of the Rosenbrock function, the Rastrigin function, the Schwefel function, the Griewangk function and the Ackley function respectively. Again, we apply both genetic algorithms: our genetic algorithm and the classic one [5]. The results are very similar to the results in the previous problem and the explanation for this difference between the algorithms is the same.

Figure 9 shows the distributions of type \mathcal{A} and type \mathcal{B} individuals in population while running our algorithm for the N -Queen Problem with $N = 25$. It shows that type \mathcal{A} individuals have higher chances to yield the best solution. This was expected since they have two solutions to the problem implemented in their structure.

5.3 The Travelling Salesman Problem

Sexual selection genetic algorithms were applied in [16] using a rather complex competitive/co-operative operators and sexual selection. Their approach models the competitive male behaviour observed in nature, and it also includes a selection policy based on co-operative fitness for the female selection. The mutation rates used in the algorithm take into account gender-based differences. The model was tested on the well-known Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) and compare it with the standard genetic algorithm model applied to the same problem with the same setup where it is appropriate. Their model produces substantially better results than the standard model.

Fig. 3: Average (over 20 runs) Fitness Function Value vs. Number of Generations for Rosenbrock Function with 10 variables

Here we compare our proposed type-based genetic algorithm with their sexual selection genetic algorithm. We test our model on the same TSP problem with the same setup used in [16], e.g. the same chromosome structure, population size, number of generations, number of trials, fitness function and the graph structure.

However, we do not use the crossover operator. The chromosome represents the list of cities to visit, e.g. 1 2 3 4 5 represents the tour $1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 1$, and we ran this problem for a graph containing 20 cities (the same number as in [16]). We use the same idea of mutation, i.e. a mutation simply swaps two cities in the chromosome. This way no illegal individuals could be produced. The population size of 200 is used and the initial population is simply produced by shuffling numbers from 1 to N for each full chromosome. Here N is the number of cities (or equivalently the size of a chromosome). The cities are laid out on the circumference of a circle and the global optimum will be a tour started at any node corresponding to a cycle through consecutive cities around the circumference. Thus, the full chromosome fitness function is defined as

$$f(C) = \frac{D}{\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} P_{m_i, m_{i+1}} + P_{m_N, m_1}},$$

where D is the minimum possible tour cost and $P_{m,n}$ represents the edge cost between nodes m and n .

We run our algorithm for 2400 generations and average it over 100 trials. The obtained results are shown in Figure 8. Our results are almost identical to the results obtained in [16]. However, our algorithm did not use any crossover operator despite the fact that there is evidence that crossover can speed up genetic

Fig. 4: Average (over 20 runs) Fitness Function Value vs. Number of Generations for Rastrigin Function with 10 variables

algorithms [18]. The algorithm does not have any special rules for individuals of different types, and a type is defined naturally by the internal structure of an individual. This greatly simplifies the mating process and the offspring production. Furthermore, the algorithm can be readily generalized and have more than 2 individual types.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

We introduced a novel type-based genetic algorithm and its application to two well-known problems. The results we obtained demonstrate that our algorithm outperforms the classic genetic algorithm (i.e. with only one type individuals with a single chromosome). Our algorithm is shown to be more stable in terms of the solution quality and also to achieve better solutions in comparison to the classic genetic algorithm after running the algorithms for the same substantial number of generations.

We intend to examine type-based genetic algorithms with more than two types, where each type is defined based on the number of full chromosomes that an individual of a respective type contains.

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Fig. 5: Average (over 20 runs) Fitness Function Value vs. Number of Generations for Schwefel Function with 10 variables

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Fig. 6: Average (over 20 runs) Fitness Function Value vs. Number of Generations for Griewangk Function with 10 variables

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Fig. 7: Average (over 20 runs) Fitness Function Value vs. Number of Generations for Ackley Function with 10 variables

Fig. 8: Average (over 100 runs) Fitness Function Value vs. Number of Generations for TSP Problem with 20 Cities

Fig. 9: Ratios of Individuals vs. Number of Generations